

Dynamic Behaviour of a Sandwich Beam with Internal Resonators

C.T. Sun and J.S. Chen
School of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Purdue University
West Lafayette, Indiana 47907 U.S.A.
sun@purdue.edu

SUMMARY

The dynamic behaviour of a sandwich beam with embedded internal resonators was studied. The dispersion curves and band gap structure of harmonic waves in the sandwich beam were investigated. It was found that the band gap could be shifted by the local resonance frequency of the resonator. It was demonstrated that pulses with frequencies near the resonance frequency of the internal resonators are suppressed in such a sandwich beam.

Keywords: sandwich beam; internal resonator; negative mass; wave propagation; dispersion curve

INTRODUCTION

Metamaterials have recently generated much excitement among physicists and engineers. A metamaterial is usually regarded as a material that contains man-made microstructures that give rise to unusual properties which are not found in natural materials. Researchers have found the potential to create an electromagnetic metamaterial with a negative refractive index which is not found in natural materials. The concept of left-handed (LH) metamaterials was first introduced by Veselago [1]. An LH metamaterial having negative permittivity and permeability behaves oppositely to right-handed materials. Several decades later following Veselago's work, LH metamaterials gained significant attention after Pendry [2] proposed the possibility of making perfect lens by using them.

Due to the mathematical analogy between acoustic and electromagnetic waves, researchers have recently attempted to find the counterpart of LH metamaterials in acoustic waves. Basically, it is to create metamaterials that possess negative stiffness and negative mass density. To date, most of the work in acoustic metamaterials is, however, theoretical in nature except for metamaterials with negative effective mass or mass density which can be realized with manmade microstructures. Liu et al. [3] investigated a type of composite fabricated using lead balls coated with silicon rubber embedded in an epoxy matrix. Near the local resonance frequencies, the composite behaves as a material with effective negativity in mass density. Such an anomalous response of the system is the consequence of the coupling of the long-wavelength elastic wave in the host medium with the localized vibration motion of the lead spheres. Recently, Milton and Willis [4] and Huang et al. [5] presented a theoretical foundation for the concept of negative effective mass by considering a different microstructure

model. One particular form of acoustic metamaterials whose microstructures consist of internal degrees of freedom inside the host medium has been investigated by Huang and Sun [6]. It was shown that these metamaterials exhibit unusual dynamic behavior and are good candidates for filtering low-frequency sound and vibration.

SANWICH BEAM WITH INTERNAL RESONATORS

In a typical sandwich construction, the face sheets are the major load-bearing components and the lightweight core is used to support the face sheets and take the transverse shear force. A weakness of sandwich structures is their low impact resistant strength and impact energy absorption capability. In the present study, we propose to add a very important function in the core for blocking incident blast wave and increasing the capability in storing temporarily the impact energy. Figure 1 shows a design of such a sandwich construction with a foam core that contains distributed “rigid” containers that are embedded in the foam core. Inside each container there is an internal mass/resonator supported by a spring. These internal masses act more or less like those internal resonators in acoustic metamaterials [4-6].

Figure 1 Sandwich beam with internal resonators.

In the sandwich beam, each resonator consists of a mass m and a linear spring with a spring constant denoted by k . By employing an energy averaging technique, the deformation energy and kinetic energy per unit length for the sandwich beam are obtained as

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ EI \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \right)^2 + GA \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \varphi \right)^2 \right\} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{k}{a} (v_1 - v)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} (\rho A \dot{v}^2 + \rho I \dot{\varphi}^2) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{m}{a} \dot{v}_1^2 \quad (2)$$

respectively, where GA is transverse shear rigidity, EI is bending rigidity, ρA is mass of the sandwich beam per unit length, ρI is rotary inertia, v and φ are the transverse displacement and rotation of the sandwich beam, respectively, v_1 is the transverse displacement of the internal mass, and a is the spacing of the internal masses. By using the Hamilton's principle, the equations of motion for the sandwich beam are obtained as

$$\begin{aligned}
GA(v'' + \varphi') - \rho A \ddot{v} + \frac{k}{a}(v_1 - v) &= 0 \\
EI\varphi'' - GA(v' + \varphi) - \rho I \ddot{\varphi} &= 0 \\
\frac{k}{a}(v_1 - v) + \frac{m}{a}\ddot{v}_1 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

DISPERSION CURVES

For harmonic waves, the three displacement functions v , φ , and v_1 all contain the wave form $e^{i(qx - \omega t)}$ in which q is wave number and ω is angular frequency. The dispersion equation can be readily obtained as

$$A_1\omega^6 + A_2\omega^4 + A_3\omega^2 + A_4 = 0 \tag{4}$$

where $A_1 = -\rho I \rho A \left(\frac{m}{a}\right)$,

$$A_2 = \left\{ (\rho IGA + EI\rho A) \left(\frac{m}{a}\right) q^2 + GA\rho A \left(\frac{m}{a}\right) + \rho I \rho A \left(\frac{k}{a}\right) + \left(\frac{km}{a^2}\right) \rho I \right\},$$

$$\begin{aligned}
A_3 = - \left\{ EIGA \left(\frac{m}{a}\right) q^4 + \left\{ (\rho IGA + EI\rho A) \left(\frac{k}{a}\right) + \left(\frac{km}{a^2}\right) EI \right\} q^2 + GA\rho A \left(\frac{k}{a}\right) \right. \\
\left. + \left(\frac{km}{a^2}\right) GA \right\}, \quad A_4 = EIGA \left(\frac{k}{a}\right) q^4.
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 2 shows the three branches of the dispersion curves of harmonic waves propagating in a sandwich beam of infinite extent. The dimensions and material parameters adopted in the calculations are listed in Table 1. The face sheets are IM7/953-2A $[0/90]_{2S}$ laminates with an effective elastic modulus E_f ; the core material is Rohacell IG-3 with elastic shear modulus G_c . The thicknesses of the sheet and the core are denoted by h_f and h_c , respectively, and b denotes the width of the beam. The densities of the face sheet and the core are 1600 kg/m^3 and 32 kg/m^3 , respectively. Table 2 summarizes the bending rigidity, shear stiffness, mass per unit length, and rotary inertia of the sandwich beam. The accuracy of the present sandwich beam model is evaluated by comparing the results obtained from theoretical model given by equation (4) with those obtained by a finite element analysis based on the original discrete mass model.

Table 1 Dimension and material constants of the face feet and the core.

E_f (GPa)	G_c (MPa)	h_f (m)	h_c (m)	b (m)	a (m)	k (N/m)	m (kg)
92	10	0.001	0.025	0.025	0.01	10^3	10^{-2}

Table 2 Properties of the sandwich beam.

$EI(Pa \cdot m^4)$	$GA(Pa \cdot m^2)$	$\rho A(kg/m)$	$\rho I(kg \cdot m)$
776.25	6.75×10^3	0.1	1.4542×10^{-5}

In figure 2, the normalized angular frequency is defined as $\bar{\omega} = \omega/\omega_0$ where $\omega_0 = \sqrt{k/m} = 316 \text{ rad/sec}$ is the local resonance frequency of the resonator, and $\bar{q} = qa$ is dimensionless wave number. It is noted that there is a band gap between $\bar{\omega} = 1$ and $\bar{\omega} = 3.317$. Theoretically, in this frequency range, harmonic waves cannot propagate. The aforementioned phenomenon may be explained more explicitly by investigating the nature of the dimensionless wave number for wave frequencies within the band gap. For this purpose, the dispersion equation, equation (4), can be viewed as an equation for wave number q as a function of frequency ω . For a given frequency ω the solution for wave number can be calculated from equation (4). The solution may be complex in the form of $\bar{q} = aq = \alpha + i\beta$. If β exists, then the wave amplitude should exhibit a spatial decay. This is why β is referred to as ‘‘attenuation factor.’’ Of interest is that when wave frequency approaches the local resonance frequency ω_0 , the attenuation factor β becomes unbounded. In other words, the maximum wave attenuation would be attained at the local resonance.

Figure 2 Dispersion curves for harmonic waves: three branches.

Figure 3 Attenuation factor as a function of dimensionless frequency $\bar{\omega}$.

CONTINUUM REPRESENTATION

If the sandwich beam with internal resonators is treated as a conventional sandwich beam with an effective core, then the equations of motion reduce to

$$\begin{aligned} GA(v'' + \phi') - (\rho A)_{eff} \ddot{v} &= 0 \\ EI\phi'' - GA(v' + \phi) - \rho I \ddot{\phi} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

in which $(\rho A)_{eff}$ is the effective mass per unit length. The dispersion equation based on this model can be expressed as

$$GA EI q^4 - (GA \rho I \omega^2 + EI (\rho A)_{eff} \omega^2) q^2 + (\rho I \omega^2 - GA) (\rho A)_{eff} \omega^2 = 0 \quad (6)$$

To truly represent the original sandwich beam with resonators, the equivalent mass $(\rho A)_{eff}$ of this representative sandwich beam has to be chosen so that the dispersion curves match those of the exact ones presented in figure 2. The result is

$$(\rho A)_{eff} = \frac{GA \rho I \omega^2 - GA EI q^4}{\{\rho I \omega^2 - GA - EI q^2\} \omega^2} \quad (7)$$

Since the dispersion curves obtained from equation (4) give the solution of q^2 in terms of frequency ω , thus, $(\rho A)_{eff}$ can be considered as a function of frequency alone. Consequently, the dimensionless frequency-dependent mass per unit length $(\rho A)_{eff} / \rho A$ can be depicted as a function of frequency as shown in figure 4. It is seen that when wave frequency approaches the local resonance (*i.e.*, $\bar{\omega} \rightarrow 1$), the effective mass becomes unbounded. Moreover, the effective mass becomes negative if $\bar{\omega} > 1$. In fact, the frequency region of negative effective mass coincides with the band gap.

Figure 4 Dimensionless effective mass per unit length.

TRANSIENT RESPONSE

Wave Propagation

Consider a long sandwich beam with resonators as shown in figure 1. The left end is assumed to be actuated with a prescribed displacement given by

$$\begin{aligned} v(t) &= v_0 \sin \omega t & t \geq 0 \\ v(t) &= 0 & t \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The corresponding frequency spectrum of the actuation for $\omega = 319.4$ rad/sec (or $\omega/\omega_0 = 1.01$) is shown in figure 5. It is evident that the dominant forcing frequency is $\omega = 319.4$ rad/sec. The deformed shape of the first 4 m of the sandwich beam at time 0.439 sec is displayed in figure 6(a). Figure 6(b) shows the snap shot of the vertical motions of the internal masses at time 0.439 sec. The results of figures 6(a) and 6(b) clearly show a significant spatial decay of amplitude of the flexural motion of the beam. In other words, the motion produced by the actuation at the left end is forbidden to propagate into the sandwich beam. It is also noted that the amplitude of vibration of the internal masses is more than an order of magnitude larger than that of the sandwich beam. This indicates that a much greater portion of the actuation work is stored in the resonators especially in those near the actuated end.

For the purpose of comparison, the same sandwich beam with rigidly attached (simulated with a large value of k) internal masses is also studied using the same actuation with the result shown in figure 7. In this case, the generated wave basically can propagate along the sandwich beam without attenuation.

Figure 5 Frequency spectrum of the displacement actuation.

Figure 6 Mode shape at time 0.439 sec for (a) sandwich beam deflection v and (b) displacements of the resonators.

Figure 7 Deformed shape at time 0.439 sec of a reference sandwich beam with rigidly attached internal masses.

Filtering of Disturbance

A sandwich beam having a section with resonators as shown in figure 8 can be used as a band filter. For illustration, we consider two sets of resonators with different local resonance frequencies, $\omega_{01} = 1005$ rad/sec and $\omega_{02} = 316$ rad/sec, are placed sequentially at the mid section of the sandwich beam and the length of each section is 30cm. The first set of the local resonators can be regarded as a high-pass filter while the next a low-pass filter. An excitation consisting of the superposition of two harmonic excitations is applied to the free end of the beam, *i.e.*,

$$v(t) = v_0(\sin \omega_1 t + \sin \omega_2 t) \quad t \geq 0 \quad (8)$$

In the numerical solutions, we select $\omega_1 / \omega_{01} = 1.01$ and $\omega_2 / \omega_{02} = 1.01$. Figure 9(a) shows the incident wave generated in the sandwich beam before it hits the section with resonators. Figure 9(b) shows the comparison of the responses of the beams with and without the local resonators, respectively. It is noted that, after the wave passes through the section with resonators, the wave amplitude is significantly reduced. In contrast, no appreciable change in wave amplitude is seen in the sandwich without resonators. It is also noted that there is a significant reflection of incident wave from the section with resonators to the section without resonators.

Figure 8 Sandwich beam with a section containing two different resonators.

Figure 9 Wave profile at time $t=0.015$ sec; (a) incident wave; (b) comparison between sandwich beams with and without resonators.

Additional insight of the filtering phenomenon can be obtained by analyzing the frequency spectrum at different locations of the sandwich beam. The spectrum analysis of the response in the first section of the sandwich without resonators is shown in figure 10. As expected, two peaks occur at the excitation frequencies. Figures 11(a) and 11(b) show the frequency responses, respectively, after the wave passes through the first section and the second section with resonators. It is clearly shown that the intensity of the wave with frequency ω_1 decreases conspicuously after it travels through the first filter. As the wave passes through the second section with resonators of local resonance frequency ω_{02} , the frequency content of ω_2 is also greatly reduced.

Figure 10 Spectrum analysis of the incident wave ($\omega^* = \omega / \omega_1$).

Figure 11 Spectrum analysis of the wave after it passes through (a) the first section, and (b) the second section with resonators ($\omega^* = \omega / \omega_1$).

CONCLUSION

In this study, the dynamic behaviour of a sandwich beam with internal resonators was shown to be quite different from that of the conventional sandwich beam. Equations of motions for sandwich beams with resonators have been derived and employed to study wave propagation. It was shown that waves with frequencies that are close to the local resonance frequency of the resonator can be stopped in such a sandwich beam. It was found that, in order to establish an effective Timoshenko beam model with the same dispersion behaviour of the original sandwich beam with resonators, a negative effective mass per unit length in certain frequency range is needed. The resonators embedded in the sandwich beam can be used to tailor the band gap structure and employed to forbid waves of certain frequencies from propagating in the sandwich beam.

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